

CHRONIC VASOMOTOR RHINOPATHY AS A SYNONYM FOR CHRONIC ALLERGIC RHINOPATHY

Shodiyeva Elmira Yusupjonova

Assistant of the Department of Otorhinolaryngology and
Stomatology of Fergana Medical Institute of Public Health

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10023750>

Abstract. The informationally significant symptoms of chronic allergic rhinopathy (CAR) and chronic vasomotor rhinopathy (CVR) identified using the developed algorithm and their justified diagnostic significance for both nosologies give reason to consider chronic vasomotor rhinopathy a synonym for chronic allergic rhinopathy.

Keywords: chronic vasomotor rhinopathy, chronic allergic rhinopathy, information-significant symptoms, synonym.

INTRODUCTION

According to modern literature, there are no reliable clinical and rhinoscopic signs to differentiate chronic allergic rhinopathy (CAR) and chronic vasomotor rhinopathy (CVR). Often, at the first visit to the doctor, the diagnosis of vasomotor rhinitis cannot be made and requires dynamic observation. Even if you exclude the diagnosis of allergic rhinitis using standard methods, you cannot completely reject the allergic nature of the disease, which is often confirmed after a certain period of time, which leads to a revision of the diagnosis, and the treatment of these nasal nosologies is identical [1]. The European Academy of Allergy and Clinical Immunology (EAACI) does not recommend using the term vasomotor rhinitis when making a diagnosis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The purpose of the study is to establish information-significant symptoms of chronic allergic and chronic vasomotor rhinopathies using the developed algorithm and to substantiate their diagnostic significance for these nosologies.

According to the developed patient examination card, which included complaints, anamnesis, concomitant pathologies, objective status, tests and autonomic tone, 30 men aged 18 to 61 years, 44 women aged 19 to 71 years with a diagnosis of chronic alveolar disease were examined - allergic rhinopathy and 125 men aged 15 to 67 years, 128 women aged 18 to 64 years diagnosed with chronic vasomotor rhinopathy based on 77 symptoms.

When processing questionnaires for examining patients with chronic allergic and chronic vasomotor rhinopathy, symptoms were grouped into categories and had an equal number (77) for both diseases. The "Treatment" category, which included 14 items, was excluded from the list and it was decided

not to use it. The symptoms of hyperthyroidism and hypothyroidism were also excluded from the category “Concomitant pathologies”, which appeared only once in these lists. The numbering of symptoms was changed from 1 to 61. Next, filtering No. 2 was carried out, which indicated symptoms (zero symptoms) in the amount of 11.

In table 1 shows zero symptoms that were not encountered in the study with one or another form of rhinopathy even once.

Table 1

Zero symptoms removed (proportion of sample size)

№	Symptom	Men		Women	
		CAR	CVR	CAR	CVR
1 6	Hay fever	0,3 00	0	0,25 0	0
1 9	Allergy history is negative	0	0,6 8	0,02 3	0,492
2 0	Skin tests positive	0,2 33	0	0,20 5	0
3 0	Enterocolitis	0	0,0 48	0	0,016
3 5	Vegetovascular dystonia	0	0,0 4	0,04 6	0,156
3 9	Chronic tonsillitis	0	0,0 64	0,06 8	0,109
4 5	Vojacek's blue spots	0	0,4 24	0	0,430
5 1	Mucous discharge	0,0 67	0,0 48	0	0,055
5 2	Discharge mucopurulent	0	0,0 16	0	0,008
5 6	Lymphocytosis	0	0,2 40	0,02 3	0,273
5 7	Skin tests positive	0,2 33	0	0,18 2	0

Note. The above null symptoms were excluded from further study. The numbering of symptoms did not change.

The interesting thing is that the symptoms that are characteristic of CAR, according to the literature, for CAR turned out to be informationally significant

for CVR. Therefore, we can conclude that these objective symptoms cannot have differential diagnostic value.

Most authors [2] believe that the presence of eosinophils in nasal secretions and blood eosinophilia determine allergies; this is a valuable diagnostic method for CAR. But there is also the opposite opinion that the absence of eosinophils in nasal secretions and blood does not exclude allergies [3]. Other authors in their studies identified blood eosinophilia in patients with vasomotor rhinopathy [4].

Using the developed algorithm for identifying informationally significant symptoms of CAR and CVR, the diagnostic significance of 26 symptoms was established, of which: 19 in men, 21 in women. But if we consider the symptoms by gender, then in men 7 symptoms turned out to be diagnostically insignificant: constant difficulty in nasal breathing, a feeling of thick mucus flowing into the throat, daily rhythm, a positive family history of allergy, atopic dermatitis, deviated nasal septum, vagotonic, and in women - 5: rhinorrhea with watery discharge, rare sneezing, positive family history of cancer, cyanotic nasal mucosa, normotonic. But 14 out of 26 symptoms had diagnostic significance: paroxysmal sneezing, no sneezing, itching in the nose, conjunctivitis, positive personal allergy history, swelling of the nasal turbinates, pallor of the nasal mucosa, swelling of the nasal mucosa, positive test with adrenaline, negative test with adrenaline, watery discharge, eosinophilia in the blood, eosinophilia in nasal discharge (more than 5 in the field of view), sympathotonic.

CONCLUSION

The occurrence of information-significant symptoms in the considered nasal pathologies suggests the recognition at the present stage of one nasal pathology with a typical triad of symptoms - chronic allergic rhinopathy. And the authors' use of the term CVR should be considered synonymous with the diagnosis of CAR, especially since the treatment of both rhinopathies is carried out according to the CAR treatment standard. This will greatly facilitate the work of doctors during the initial consultation of patients and will not require revision of the diagnosis during further observation.

References:

1. Blotsky A.A., Valova N.V. Application of a semiconductor high-energy laser in patients with various forms of allergic rhinitis // Ros. rhinol. 2010. No. 3. P. 17.
2. Lopatin A. S. Vasomotor rhinitis: pathogenesis, diagnosis and principles of treatment: clinical recommendations / Ed. A. S. Lopatina. M., 2014. 25 p.

3. Pletneva I. E., Portenko G. M., Shmatov G. P. Method for selecting information-significant symptoms of chronic allergic and chronic vasomotor rhinopathies // Ros. otorhinolaryngology. 2016. Appendix. pp. 100–104.
4. Daynyak L. B. Vasomotor rhinitis. M.: Medicine, 2016. 176 p.
5. Kalinin M. A. Rhinitis is an eternal problem. Ways to “mitigate” it // Effective pharmacotherapy. 2011. No. 36. pp. 36–37.
6. Lapteva N. A. On the issue of neurogenic reflex runny nose // Vestn. otorhinolaryngology. 2012. No. 6. pp. 22–28.

